

ON the impossibility of not being Pascalian.

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The works of Blaise Pascal have been a source of inspiration ever since were written. The eloquence of his brilliant quotes will help me unravel his thought about science, knowledge, love, philosophy and life him being a $\mu\alpha\tau\eta\mu\alpha\tau\epsilon\sigma$ of his time.

This paper intends to be a comprehensive gnoseological analysis of Pascal's view of the different dimensions, reality beholds.

Childhood

Pascal was born in a low-noblesse French family in 1623. The second between two sisters. He had poor health which influenced his thought with aches, nervousness and melancholy.

At the age of three he lost his mother, moving to Paris his father took charge of his education which was very polished making him feel sure he could accomplish all his goals. He was outstanding in the reading of the classic humanists. His father marked a clear distinction between scientific and religious matters.

Being eleven years old, he came up with the 32nd proposition of Euclid's¹ elements, which shows his speculative ability. He belonged to the French intellectual circle along with Fermat, Marsenne, Gassendi, Roberval, Carcavi and Descartes among others.

Back in those days the difference among the sciences and philosophy was not very clear, making Pascal "a man of science", moreover a cultural referent.

¹ *In any triangle, if one of the sides is produced, then the exterior angle equals the sum of the two interior and opposite angles, and the sum of the three interior angles of the triangle equals two right angles.*

Let ABC be a triangle, and let one side of it BC be produced to D .
I say that the exterior angle ACD equals the sum of the two interior and opposite angles CAB and ABC , and the sum of the three interior angles of the triangle ABC , BCA , and CAB equals two right angles.

Draw CE through the point C parallel to the straight line, AB . Since AB is parallel to CE , and AC falls upon them, therefore the alternate angles BAC and ACE equal one another. Again, since AB is parallel to CE , and the straight line, BD falls upon them, therefore the exterior angle ECD equals the interior and opposite angle ABC . But the angle ACE was also proved equal to the angle BAC . Therefore, the whole angle ACD equals the sum of the two interior and opposite angles BAC and ABC . Add the angle ACB to each. Then the sum of the angles ACD and ACB equals the sum of the three angles ABC , BCA , and CAB . Add the angle ACB to each. Then the sum of the angles ACD and ACB equals the sum of the three angles ABC , BCA , and CAB . But the sum of the angles ACD and ACB equals two right angles. Therefore, the sum of the angles ABC , BCA , and CAB also equals two right angles. Therefore, in any triangle, if one of the sides is produced, then the exterior angle equals the sum of the two interior and opposite angles, and the sum of the three interior angles of the triangle equals two right angles.

Once, intrigued by the noise a knife made when fallen on a plate, and how it stopped placing his hand over it, Pascal explained it in his *Treaty of Sound* through his theories of the conical bodies giving light to what we know today as Pascal’s Theorem or mystical hexagon:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a + b)^0 &= 1 \\
 (a + b)^1 &= a + b \\
 (a + b)^2 &= a^2 + 2ab + b^2 \\
 (a + b)^3 &= a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3 \\
 (a + b)^4 &= a^4 + 4a^3b + 6a^2b^2 + 4ab^3 + b^4 \\
 (a + b)^5 &= a^5 + 5a^4b + 10a^3b^2 + 10a^2b^3 + 5ab^4 + b^5
 \end{aligned}$$

But his contribution was not only theoretical. To help his father who was a tax collector and did a great deal of calculations he developed at 19, an “arithmetic machine” which came to be known as Pascalline: our former calculator². The ample possibilities of such artifice were evident.

This brief introduction of the accomplishments of his early years shows a vivid and profoundly imaginative mind: his creations are innovative, exact, and harmonic all these adjectives encompass beauty.

These show the aesthetics in his pragmatic work. Looking closely into his creative process, developed at a very young and innocent age, is quite illuminating for the needed gnoseological construction:

- “You wouldn’t search for it if you hadn’t already found it”

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- “Commonly, we are more persuaded by the reasons we have found than by those found by others”
- “For those who want to see there is enough light, for those with the opposite disposition there is always enough darkness”
- “Too weak is our reason if it cannot understand there are many things that exceed it”
- “Rest is not the destiny of man, and security is only an illusion”
- “Men have illusions as birds do wings: it is what sustains them”
- “Reason works slowly, with so many visions, on so many principles, that at every moment it falls asleep or gets lost. Passion works in an instant”.

For a loved, well raised and profoundly educated kid, the seed gave fruit in this quotes: sparks of wisdom, which draw how his mind set dialogued with the phenomena that caught his eye. The speculative mind of his time, was conceived to be the mirror of reality, so when he found a gap in the path he sensed where to aim: there was something to discover. This procedure explains why reasons found personally are more convincing than borrowed ones. Looking closely at the equation to solve or the mystery to clear the light is enough for the one whose intention is strong, but too dim for the pusillanimous. Nonetheless, certain matters exceed our reason and should be addressed otherwise. Nevertheless, what keeps human life going is the colonization of our mirror-mind with the brilliance of nature. The human task is to open these paths of reflection, without blurring it, ignoring or omitting elements of each cognitive or sentient dimension. Such is the illusion that keeps us going forward, to rest is unthinkable.

The different approaches or dimensions in which the mind encounters reality need to be intertwined at their own pace and speed, reason cannot produce this weft alone, passion –the is indispensable.

This Gordian knot between the practical and theoretical intellect will be the internal compass of Pascal’s legacy to us. His creative process is the perfect weft of reason and passion in the exact dosage.

Youth

Around this time Blaise comes closer to Christianity through Jansenism: a literal interpretation of Augustinian thought.

In 1647, being 23 years old, he meets with Descartes. The *rendezvous* is not only historic but rather straightforward on the discrepancy of both characters: In his *Penseés*³, he refers to Descartes as useless and uncertain, on the other hand, Rene said Blaise had “too much vacuum in the head”, alluding to Pascal’s studies on vacuum, which he only knew too well.

How can something exist in nothingness? Was one of the hot issues that worried both thinkers and everyone else in those days. Therefore, Pascal looked at it closely. He wrote “New Experiments on the Void” where he tried to approach it through an experimental method, which was in fact his true objective: to demonstrate that scientific results could be obtained through observation and experimentation. Sadly for posterity, Descartes *ouvre* had more circulation.

Even though Pascal’s his study not only brought an impeccable method but also produced the invention of the plunger syringe we still use today, a void inside a glass test tube, as a practical demonstration of his accurate analysis of reality: theoretically and practically. Not only mirroring the magnificence of nature but adapting its use for human needs. This path moved him away of

³ PASCAL B. 1670. *Pensées de M. Pascal sur la religion et sur quelque autres Sujets*. Paris: Guillaume Desprée.

the prevailing rationalism which filled the mouth of his critics, but this only fueled his wits making him focus in one objective: to demonstrate that there is <something> in what we call <nothing>, as a physical matter, not merely conceptually.

The experiment described in his *Traité de l'Equilibre des Liqueurs*⁴ was a huge achievement because it thoroughly demonstrates how it happens that atmospheric pressure causes the so called “*horror vacui*” in the bodies, due to the relationship of their weight and the pressure of the air. He was very proud of this work, even saying it absolutely concludes the subject. And dissipated the alternative theological explanations for the matter, which also arose displeasure among the Jesuites.

Much of which is expressed in his quotes:

- Men will always deny what he fails to understand.
- The greatness of man is knowing how to recognize his own smallness
- We possess Truth and Good only in part, and mixed with falsehood and evil.
- Nature is an infinite sphere which center is everywhere and its circumference is nowhere.
- The imagination disposes of everything: it makes beauty, justice and happiness, that is, the totality of the world.
- I will not have more even if I have worlds. If it were for space, the universe would surround me and swallow me like an atom; but by thought I embrace the world.

From the fact that through observation he could produce a) practical inventions, b) induce broader explanations of conceptual dimensions and link how he saw his critics benevolently in the awareness they could not yet see what he was seeing. All the same he was clear that was not all there is to know anyway. Our place to peek into reality is minuscule and before that, we should know –and conquer- ourselves firstly, because falsehood and evil are lurking. Even though, the real human motor is imagination –that is the capacity of creation- meaning, the recreation of nature in thought, which is the true humane way to do so beautifully, justly and happily, this is the only way we may turn nature infinite. The issue of time is the solution to the Gordian knot and core of today’s difficulties: and therefore, the path to surpassing our own selves.

- We know the truth not only by reason, but also by the heart.
- The heart has reasons that reason does not understand.
- I must not seek my dignity in space, but in the government of my thought.
- What is seen frequently is not amazing... What has never been seen, when it happens, is considered a prodigy.
- Faith says what the senses do not say, but not the opposite of what they see. She is above them but not against them.
- If you don't act like you think, you'll end up thinking like you act.
- Philosophy consists in laughing at philosophy.

Under the light of Pascal’s thought, he draws the steps to wisdom quite clearly acknowledging the truths of the heart as the guidelines to reason and even more prodigious when well grasped, being these the guidelines for our conduct which we shall follow to build our integrity, and in this way, “may each one find within his law, his peace through his light”.

⁴ PASCAL B. 1663. *Traitez de l'Equilibre des Liqueurs, et de la Pesanteur de la masse de l'air*. Paris: Guillaume Desprée.

The previous introductory analyses of Pascal's empirical and theoretical ability to face the different dimensions of reality, and order its cognitive steps without overlooking any element and not losing it in his head in the quest, is not only remarkable but quite illuminating for the way to manage reality has temporal individual consequences not only in personal life, as well as historical ones, which societies undergo in terms of politics and economy.

This are VERY complicated times world-wide concerning both issues.

I shall walk you through two possible scenarios using Arrow's impossibility theorem⁵.

Arrow's work: *Social Choice and Individual Values*⁶, shows that the task of constructing a social welfare function to reflect the aims and aspirations of a free democratic society is an impossible one. Arrow has proved a general theorem about the impossibility of constructing an ordering for society as whole, which in some way reflect all the individual orderings of the members who make up the society. Arrow's main concern is to consider if a social choice can be satisfactorily derived from individual decisions. The problem is easily solved by dictatorship under which social decisions are made by single individual in small group. In a democratic society, each, and every individual will have their idea of social welfare function. It is therefore difficult to construct a social welfare function which reflects the individual orderings.

The political problem described by Arrow is -more or less-, what most of the countries around the world are going through. Every political and economic system has turned insufficient to answer the needs and expectations of the people. The issue may be proven locally everywhere, methodologically, logically, empirically, emotionally. This Gordian knot is the connection between the individual-social, the theoretical-practical. Why does everyone feel so lost?

And society –as we know it- is going havoc?

Scenario 1: The Cartesian division of *res cogitans* and *extensa* which derived into the rationalistic and empirical way to deal with reality, divided profoundly the epistemic status of apprehensive thought: making prevail one over the other, it rendered poisoned fruits such as the industrial revolution along with capitalism and inconsistencies such as nihilism and many other ism's. At first, such division lead from academic discussion, to wars between supposed ideals, to oblivion of entire realms of society (minorities, vulnerable groups), to general ignorance or even perplexity of how to face and solve problems or even find happiness. What can be worse for us humans than to feel strange in our own land? It is the next step to paradise lost. All of us have experienced this to some extent, unfortunately too many in a pitiful manner: the statistical numeralia of famine, war, poverty, unhealth, overpopulation, migration, injustice, unfreedom, unhappiness is overwhelming. These two extreme poles come to an impossible intertwining proof in Kenneth Arrow's impossibility theorem which exemplifies, to some extent, today's economic and political crises worldwide.

Scenario 2: Until recently, we have come to learn how both cerebral hemispheres manage the intellectual capacities by the left one and the creative abilities by the right side, and work harmonically as our two arms do. Pascal could somehow sense the consequences of this

⁵ ARROW K.J. et Al., 2014. The Arrow Impossibility Theorem. USA: Columbia University Press.

⁶ Published in 1951.

impossible fracture Descartes promoted overcoming it through the amplitude of his concept of nature from where knowledge starts, then, speculatively mind-mirroring it through the senses which can be ordered and explained methodically integrated gradually and on the spot, other cognitive variables -from the other hemisphere-, be them intuitive, observed, induced, deduced, derived, imagined, in whatever way. Pascal unveiled this epistemological path step by step, all the way to the extreme of his faith. And felt pride and joy in the process as he states in his written legacy.

Pascal's intelligence pendulum was not linear but circular, encompassing every element the moment it appears to an observing and meticulous intellect. But the real change of scenery comes from the conjunction of the role of the will: -the heart-. Decisions are not taken from the theoretical reasons of the brain BUT from the bottom of the heart as well. This is exactly how Arrow's riddle is solved: the unity between will (practical-empirical) and reason (theoretical-rational) is what unties the Gordian knot. This is the core of decision: WILL is the spring that can shrink when personal or familiar decisions are at stake (unselfishness) or stretch when community or social cooperation is due (magnanimity): these are social decisions: political and economic, which should be thought through and wanted. But there is another very important dimension which affects all these weft and woof of the variable weave Pascal proposes: TEMPORALITY. The core of decision-taking is the present, the HERE and NOW. We truly own only the present moment, the course our actions imprint on the world is done timely. The help someone in need should be immediate not a promise for the future. Political decisions are to solve present social issues, any other way is demagoguery the same is true for economic decisions: Arrow's theorem design is possible based on the fissure of *res cogitans* and *res extensa* it separates the rational and real realms: it has no heart. Is there any doubt stress and the mental disorders are the sickness of the past and present century caused precisely by the ill management of time? Either we manage the unity of intellect and will: govern ourselves or we will continue to brake from the inside out. Our societies are probably the crashed mirror of our minds. And so, Pascal goes on:

- I do not believe in revolutions that alter the order of things but don't change the human heart.
- Only mediocrity suits. This has been established by plurality, and it bites anyone who escapes from it somewhere.
- The virtues of a man should not be measured by his efforts but by his daily deeds.

BUT,

- Know that man infinitely surpasses man.

So, there is hope! Following the Pascalian teachings:

Existentialism, -as we all well know, in this forum- is essentially turning our hearts toward the here and now. And, being LOVE defined as the union of understanding and will -the very existential choice- it is the only possible shock absorber of the new *οικονομία* born here from, the only possible path for society to survive.

Thank-you.